

Reading About Science Communication

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Key Words

Science Communication
Books

Summary

Lately the science communication book market has become quite lively. Several books have been published over the past few years. Covering topics from more formal science communication to practical writing, these books are important resources for everyone.

Investigating Science
Communication in the
Information Age: Implications
for public engagement and
popular media
OUP Oxford
320 pages
ISBN 978-0199552665

Practising Science
Communication in the
Information Age: Theorising
professional practices
OUP Oxford
264 pages
ISBN 978-0199552672

Investigating and Practising Science Communication in the Information Age is a two volume collection of commissioned chapters by well known science communicators and scholars. This makes the books a valuable resource for teaching, researching and practicing science communication.

Investigating brings a strong sociological background to science communication, examining recent trends in the theory and research of science communication. *Practising*, on the other hand, provides a thorough introduction to anyone wishing to start implementing projects and activities in contemporary science communication. Definitely two books worth reading.

Don't Be Such a Scientist
Randy Olson
Island Press
216 pages
ISBN 978-1597265638

Randy Olson experienced a huge life change when he moved from the top of the academic tree and a tenured professorship at the University of New Hampshire to being a student at the University of Southern California School Of Cinema. This career shift gave Olson some first-hand experience in identifying the problems and solutions for modern visual science communication. For Olson, the important point to remember is that the general public don't speak science. The solution, he argues, is to stay true to the facts while tapping into something more primordial, more irrational, and more human, bridging the gap between education and entertainment. The book presents great tips and advice for scientists who want to communicate and cinematographers who want to entertain and educate with film.

Eloquent Science
David M. Schultz
American Meteorological Society
412 pages
ISBN 978-1-878220-91-2

Following up from a communication workshop organised by the American Meteorological Society, this book is a good reference for scientists, and especially for atmospheric scientists. The book touches on different aspects of intra-community communication, writing papers, reports, preparing presentations to be delivered in conferences and workshops, etc. Even though the book covers such a wide range of topics, one shortcoming is its treatment of public and media communication, as the author only dedicates six pages out of 412 to this important aspect of modern science communication for researchers. This is a great companion for scientists who must write and present their research, but is not intended as a book for science communicators.

Handbook of Public
Communication of Science and
Technology
Edited by Massimiano Bucchi & Brian
Trench
Routledge
263 pages
ISBN 978-0-415-38617-3

There is no need to say that the public communication of science and technology is a rapidly expanding component of communication. Combining contributions from different disciplines (media and journalism studies, sociology and the history of science), the perspectives of different geographical and cultural contexts, and selecting key contributions from well-respected authors, these original texts provide an interdisciplinary as well as a global approach to the public communication of science and technology. This handbook brings many general overviews together, balanced by a conceptual knowledge of the practical problems faced by practitioners with a thorough review of relevant research issues. It provides a useful introduction to new trends in the public communication of science and technology in various parts of the world, and is particularly sensitive to international issues.

Introduction Science Communication
Edited by Mark L. Brake & Emma Weitkamp
Palgrave Macmillan
177 pages
ISBN 978-0-230-57386-4

Mark Brake and Emma Weitkamp are both lecturers in Science Communication in the UK, a country with a long tradition in science communication. The UK is the birthplace of social, political and academic movements like the public understanding of science (PUS), the public communication of science and technology (PCST), and more recently the public engagement of science (PES). Mark and Emma worked with colleagues and have put together a nice introduction to science communication. With a good balance between the theoretical and practical aspects of science communication, the book discusses key methods and gives great tips for science communication in many areas, from working with science centres and museums, to the best way to approach popular science writing and broadcasting. For a book published in early 2010, it omits an important part of modern science communication: the use of new media, such as blogs, social networks, viral communication and new ways of community engagement.

Biography

Pedro Russo is the Global Coordinator for IYA2009 working at the European Southern Observatory for the IAU. He is a member of the Venus Monitoring Camera/Venus Express Scientific Team and has been working with Europlanet, IAU Commission 55: Communicating Astronomy with the Public, EGU Earth and Space Science Informatics Division and the IAF Science and Society Committee.